

Production of hydrochar fuel by microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation of olive pomace slurry from olive oil industry for combustion application

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ABSTRACT

This work is the first investigation on microwave-assisted hydrothermal carbonisation (MHTC) of real olive pomace (OP) slurry from the olive oil industry to produce hydrochars with improved fuel properties for combustion applications (e.g., in boilers). Experiments were conducted based on the central composite design of response surface methodology with two main process variables: temperature (180–250 °C) and holding time (2–30 min). Severity factors ($\log R_0$) were calculated from the above variables and used to explain the process effect in a simpler way. Increasing the MHTC severity resulted in significant changes in the structure of OP (studied by FTIR and NMR analyses) as well as reductions in yield, bulk density, volatile matter, and ash content in the hydrochars. The high-severity hydrochar was positioned in the lignite zone (van Krevelen diagram). It also exhibited substantial reductions in the alkali index (86.53 %), slagging index (76.89 %), and fouling index (96.07 %) compared to the raw material. Overall, the best conditions for hydrochar production with improved combustion characteristics were found to be 250 °C for 30 min (HHV = 28.45 MJ/kg, energy densification ratio = 1.25, equilibrium moisture content = 31.1 mg/g, comprehensive combustibility index = $2.94 \times 10^{-7} \%^2 \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-3}$). These properties indicate that high-severity hydrochars could be utilised as biofuels for energy applications.

1. Introduction

Fossil fuels are non-renewable and the main source (75 %) of greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Therefore, the use of clean renewable energy is crucial to save the environment and life on earth [2]. The European Union (EU) Renewable Energy Directive II (2018/2001/EU) mandates biofuels production from non-edible lignocellulosic biomass, preferably from abundant and domestically available biomass [3]. Pyrolysis is the most commonly used process for biofuel production, which involves thermal heating of dry biomass in the absence of oxygen. It converts biomass into energy dense biochar for biofuel applications [4]. However, for the treatment of wet biomass with high water content (e.g., sewage sludge, food waste), hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC), also known as wet pyrolysis, is a preferred method. This method does not require energy-intensive steps such as dewatering and oven drying of the biomass. Wet biomass is directly pyrolysed (150–250 °C) to produce hydrochar with a high calorific value for solid biofuel applications [5].

In the prior art, HTC has been mainly reported using conventional heating systems [6]. The conventional system involves surface heat transfer mechanisms, i.e., conduction and convection, but has limitations such as longer heat exchange times and uneven heating. To overcome these limitations, several studies have recently investigated microwave-assisted hydrothermal carbonisation (MHTC) of biomass [7,8]. A microwave system operates on a dielectric heating mechanism in which the biomass particles are heated by microwave radiation. It offers the advantages of more uniform heating, faster heat exchange time, shorter processing time, and more controlled heating [9]. However, studies on the MHTC of biomasses are limited [10] and could be extended to investigate unexplored biomass such as olive pomace (OP).

The olive oil industry produces a large amount of OP (olive pulp and seeds) slurry as a residue after olive oil extraction. This material contains a very high amount of water and environmentally toxic organic contaminants such as phenols [11]. Therefore, the disposal and management of OP slurry is a major challenge. The EU is the world's leading producer (68 %) of olive oil, with a production of approximately 2

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Nomenclature			
OP	Olive pomace	AIL	Acid insoluble lignin
HTC	Hydrothermal carbonisation	HY	Hydrochar yield
MHTC	Microwave assisted hydrothermal carbonisation	VM	Volatile matter
180–2	Hydrochar produced at 180 °C with 2 min holding time	FC	Fixed carbon
180–16	Hydrochar produced at 180 °C with 16 min holding time	EMC	Equilibrium moisture content
180–30	Hydrochar produced at 180 °C with 30 min holding time	HHV	Higher heating value
215–2	Hydrochar produced at 215 °C with 2 min holding time	LHV	Lower heating value
215–16	Hydrochar produced at 215 °C with 16 min holding time	EDR	Energy densification ratio
215–30	Hydrochar produced at 215 °C with 30 min holding time	EY	Energy yield
250–2	Hydrochar produced at 250 °C with 2 min holding time	AI	Alkali index
250–16	Hydrochar produced at 250 °C with 16 min holding time	B/A	Base to acid ratio
250–30	Hydrochar produced at 250 °C with 30 min holding time	SI	Slagging index
Log R ₀	Severity factor	FI	Fouling index
		SVI	Slag viscosity index
		BAI	Bed agglomeration index

million tons per year [12]. Therefore, OP biomass is abundantly available domestically. In addition, its lignocellulosic composition shows its potential to be a suitable feedstock for the production of hydrochar for biofuel applications. Research on real OP slurry from the olive oil industry for hydrochar production is very scarce, and mainly reported the use of conventional heating systems at different process conditions such as 180–300 °C temperature and 0–24 h holding time [13–19]. They reported the production of hydrochar with a higher heating value of approximately 25–32 MJ/kg, which is comparable to coal. Regarding the use of microwave technology, Kostas et al. only documented the microwave dry pyrolysis (150–900 W for 20–240 s) of OP to produce biochar for its application as an adsorbent [20]. The MHTC of wet OP has not yet been reported in the literature. Furthermore, the effect of HTC conditions on the properties of OP hydrochar properties has not been explained using severity factors. Data on the equilibrium moisture content, a very important property that affects not only the energy value of the fuels but also their storage, transportation, and handling [21], were also not documented. Information on the corrosive elements (mainly Na and K) present in the OP hydrochar and the assessment of slagging and fouling risks caused by them were also not reported. The slagging-fouling risk assessment of the hydrochar fuel is crucial to predict its negative impact (reactor material deterioration) on the boilers and to decide on an appropriate strategy for its practical application. Optimisation of the HTC process is also rarely reported and has not been done using the widely recommended response surface methodology [22].

To resolve the aforementioned research gaps, the present study aims to evaluate the MHTC process for transforming industrial OP slurry into hydrochars with improved fuel characteristics for combustion applications, preferably in boilers. The main objectives of this work are: 1) to determine the effect of MHTC conditions on the hydrochar characteristics with the use of severity factors; 2) to establish the slagging and fouling risks for the OP and its hydrochars; 3) to predict the optimal conditions for the MHTC process on the basis of response surface methodology to produce hydrochar with the best combustion characteristics; and 4) to compare the combustion performance of the OP and its best hydrochar using TG-DSC analysis.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw material

The wet OP (fruit variety ‘Picual’) slurry with a water content of 80.43±0.17 %, were collected by a random sampling method at Almazara Andrés Aguilar, a local olive oil mill situated in Linares (Jaén), Spain (UTM coordinates: 38°04′26.86″ N, 3°38′52.31″ W).

2.2. Experiments for MHTC of wet OP

The experimental design for MHTC of wet OP slurry was based on the response surface methodology (RSM) using a face-centered central composite design (CCD) with three central points. The two experimental variables (temperature and holding time) were varied in three levels, and three replicates were performed for each operating condition, resulting in a total of thirty-three MHTC experiments. Table S1 (Supplementary Information) shows the resulting matrix for the experimental design, including both the coded and real values of the two independent variables. The MHTC was performed in a high performance microwave digestion system (Milestone Ethos One) with an ATC-400 temperature sensor and APC-55E automatic pressure control. Based on CCD, experiments were conducted with wet OP at varying temperatures of 180–250 °C and holding times of 2–30 min. The selection of the temperature range for MHTC in the present study was based on earlier studies [13,18]. Other fixed process parameters were 1500 W microwave energy, a heating rate of 22 °C/minute, and a 50 % stirring capacity. After MHTC, hydrochars were separated from liquid phase by vacuum filtration at room temperature. Thereafter, hydrochars were air-dried to reduce the moisture content and then stored in sealed plastic bags. Abbreviations used for hydrochar samples in the present article are based on MHTC temperature (°C) and holding time (min): 180–2, 180–16, 180–30, 215–2, 215–16, 215–30, 250–2, 250–16, and 250–30. For example, 180–2 means hydrochar produced at 180 °C with a 2 min holding time.

The CCD preparation for MHTC experiments and data analysis were done using Modde 6.0 statistical software (Umetrics AB, Umeå, Sweden). A second-order polynomial model (Eq. 1) was followed to study the effect of independent variables on four responses: hydrochar yield (HY), equilibrium moisture content (EMC), and higher and lower heating values of hydrochars (HHV and LHV, respectively).

$$Y = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 \cdot T_R) + (\beta_2 \cdot t_R) + (\beta_3 \cdot T_R \cdot T_R) + (\beta_4 \cdot t_R \cdot t_R) + (\beta_5 \cdot T_R \cdot t_R) \quad (1)$$

where Y is the response value, T_R and t_R are the real values of the two independent variables, and β_i ($i = 1-5$) are the intercept term (β_0), the linear effects (β_1 and β_2), the squared effects (β_3 and β_4) and the interaction effects (β_5) calculated from the experimental data by regression analysis. The statistical validation was performed by a one-way ANOVA test with a 95 % confidence level.

2.3. Severity factor calculation

The severity factor (log R_0) is a very useful parameter to study the combined effect of temperature and reaction time in the hydrothermal treatment of lignocellulosic biomass. The calculation of log R_0 is based on Eq. 2 [23]. Where t is the process time (min), $T(t)$ is the temperature

(°C) at a given time, T_r is the reference temperature (100 °C), w is a constant (equal to 14.75 for biomass) that includes the conventional energy of activation, and e is the natural base. Since the experiments were not conducted at a constant temperature during both the initial (heating) and final (cooling) stages, the severity factor for each operating condition was calculated as the sum of the severity factors determined during the heating, maintenance, and cooling stages (Eq. 3).

$$R_0 = \int_0^t e^{\frac{T(t)-T_r}{w}} dt \quad (2)$$

$$R_0 = (R_0)_{\text{heating}} + (R_0)_{\text{maintenance}} + (R_0)_{\text{cooling}} \quad (3)$$

2.4. Characterisation of raw material and hydrochar

Hydrochar yield (%) was calculated from the dry weight of hydrochar and raw OP biomass [24]. The extractive content of the samples was determined by the hexane extraction method [25]. Cellulose and hemicellulose were estimated by the detergent method [26], and the acid-insoluble lignin (AIL) was determined by the TAPPI t 222 os-74 method [27]. Bulk density (BD) is measured by the ratio of the dry weight of the samples to the volume they occupy [28]. Proximate analysis was done using a gravimetric method to estimate moisture, volatile matter (VM), fixed carbon (FC), and ash content. The moisture (M) content of the samples was determined by oven drying at 105 °C until a constant weight was achieved. The VM was determined by heating samples in a lidded ceramic crucible at 900 ± 25 °C in a furnace [29]. Ash content was estimated by heating samples at 575 ± 25 °C for 5 h in an open crucible in the muffle furnace according to the NREL/TP-510-42622 method [30]. The FC content in the samples was calculated using Eq. 4. Ultimate analysis of the samples was performed using an CHNS elemental automatic elemental analyser (TruSpec Micro, Leco, USA) to determine total carbon (C), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), and sulphur (S) content. The oxygen (O) content was calculated indirectly by the subtraction method (Eq. 5). The bomb calorimeter (Parr Series 6400, USA) was used to quantify the higher heating value (HHV) of the raw material and hydrochar samples. The lower heating value (LHV) of the samples was estimated using Eq. 6 [31]. Surface functional groups in raw materials and hydrochars were identified by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (Vertex 70 spectrophotometer, Bruker, USA) analysis in the wavelength range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} with 4 cm^{-1} resolution and 100 scans. Solid state ^{13}C NMR analysis of the samples was performed using an NMR spectrophotometer (Bruker AVANCE, USA) with a CP-MAS probe (4 mm) operating at 100.62 MHz, 2 ms contact time, and 1200 scans. The energy densification ratio (EDR) and energy yield (EY) of raw material and hydrochar samples were calculated using Eqs. 7 and 8 [18].

$$\text{FC}(\%) = 100 - (\text{M}\% + \text{VM}\% + \text{Ash}\%) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{O}(\%) = 100 - (\text{C}\% + \text{H}\% + \text{N}\% + \text{S}\% + \text{Ash}\%) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{LHV}(\text{Btu}/\text{lb}) = \text{HHV}(\text{Btu}/\text{lb}) - 10.55(\text{M}\% + 9\text{H}\%) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{EDR} = \frac{\text{HHV}_{\text{dried hydrochar}}}{\text{HHV}_{\text{dried olive pomace}}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{EY}(\%) = \text{Hydrochar yield} \times \text{EDR} \quad (8)$$

2.5. Equilibrium moisture content determination

The equilibrium moisture content (EMC) is an essential parameter used to evaluate the water sorption behavior of a porous material [21]. It was determined by measuring the changes in moisture uptake of dry olive pomace biomass and hydrochars after exposure to equilibrium conditions for several days. The experiments were conducted at 30 °C and 75 % relative humidity. The relative humidity of 75 % was achieved

by using NaCl salt solutions [28]. The tests were carried out in triplicate and the weights of the biomass and hydrochars were measured daily until no significant changes were observed. Results are reported on a moisture-free dry basis (mg of water adsorbed per gram of dry biomass).

2.6. Slagging and fouling risks evaluation

The OP and hydrochar samples were digested with a $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ mixture (3:1 ratio) in a microwave digestion system (ETHOS One, Milestone) at 140 °C, followed by ICP-OES analysis and the use of conversion factors to quantify metal oxides (Table S2, Supplementary Information). The slagging and fouling risks were assessed based on mineral composition and the use of empirical indices (Table 1) such as alkali index (AI), base to acid ratio, (B/A), slagging index (SI), fouling index (FI), slag viscosity index (SVI), and bed agglomeration index (BAI) [32–34].

2.7. Combustion performance assessment using TG-DSC

The combustion behavior of the samples was evaluated in oxidative atmosphere using a thermogravimetric (TG) analyser (TDA/SDTA 851e, Mettler Toledo, USA). The analysis conditions were an air flow of 150 mL/min and a temperature range of 25–900 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Analysis was also performed using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 822e, Mettler Toledo, USA) under oxidative conditions. The ignition temperature (T_i) was determined from the DTG curve, where the weight loss is 1 %/min after the first weight loss due to the presence of residual moisture, while the shutdown temperature (T_f) is the temperature at which the DTG reaches 1 %/min at the end of the curve [35]. The thermal reactivity of the samples was assessed using the comprehensive combustibility index (S), which was determined using Eq. 9 [36]. This equation includes the maximum $(dw/dt)_{\text{max}}$ and average rates $(dw/dt)_{\text{mean}}$ of weight loss (wt%/min).

$$S = \frac{(dw/dt)_{\text{max}} (dw/dt)_{\text{mean}}}{T_i^2 T_f} \quad (9)$$

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Structural composition of raw material and hydrochars

Holocellulose (sum of cellulose and hemicellulose), AIL, and extractives in the dry OP and hydrochar samples (produced at different severity factors) are shown in Table S2. In the present study, the severity factors are as follows: 3.050 (180°C-2 min), 3.633 (180°C-16 min), 3.874 (180°C-30 min), 4.015 (215°C-2 min), 4.647 (215°C-16 min), 4.895 (215°C-30 min), 5.071 (250°C-2 min), 5.684 (250°C-16 min), and 5.929 (250°C-30 min). The increase in temperature and holding time combined resulted in an increment in severity factor values [37]. The dry OP consisted of higher holocellulose (37.53 %), followed by AIL (36.82 %), and extractives (11.50 %). The holocellulose consisted of more hemicellulose fractions (25.39 %) than cellulose (12.15 %). In comparison to these results, Cequier et al. earlier reported a similar amount of AIL (37 ± 3.9 %), lesser holocellulose (17.6 ± 2.0 %), and higher extractive content (20 ± 1.1 %) in the OP [38]. The variations could be mainly due to differences in the proportion of pulp, stone, and peel in the dry OP.

The MHTC produced OP hydrochars with a reduced holocellulose content (2.06–30.85 %). In this holocellulose, the amount of hemicellulose in the hydrochars obtained at 3.874, 4.895, and 5.929 severity factors was relatively lower, i.e., 14.14 %, 1.70 %, and 0.0 %, respectively. This indicated that hemicellulose could be easily hydrolysed at a higher HTC temperature and a longer holding time, which might be a main reason for the reduction of holocellulose content in hydrochars. However, AIL (46.17–64.30 %) and extractive (17.62–23.97 %) fractions were enriched. Compared to dry OP, an increase in severity factor

Table 1
Methods for calculation of slagging and fouling indices.

Indicator	Equations	Slagging and Fouling risks		
		Low	Medium	High
Alkali index (AI)	$AI(\text{kg/GJ}) = \frac{\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}}{\text{HHV}(\text{GJ/kg})}$	<0.17	0.17–0.34	>0.34
Base to acid ratio (B/A)	$B/A = \frac{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{CaO} + \text{MgO} + \text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O} + \text{P}_2\text{O}_5}{\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{TiO}_2}$	-	-	-
Slagging index (SI)	$SI = B/A \times S\%$	<0.6	0.6–2.0	2.0–2.6
Fouling index (FI)	$FI = B/A \times (\text{Na}_2\text{O}\% + \text{K}_2\text{O}\%)$	0.2	0.2–0.5	0.5–1.0
Slag viscosity index (SVI)	$SVI = \text{SiO}_2 \times 100$	>72	65–72	<65
Bed agglomeration index (BAI)	$BAI = \frac{\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3}{\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}}$	-	-	<0.15

(3.05–5.93) resulted in a 26.33–74.60 % increase in AIL and a 53.18–108.37 % increase in extractive content. The hydrochar produced at a severity factor of 5.929 contained relatively higher AIL (64.30 %) and extractives (23.75 %), at the expense of lower holocellulose (2.96 %) contents. This is a favorable attribute of hydrochar for biofuel application because higher lignin and extractives could increase its heating value [39,40]. In agreement with the present results, Najafi et al. also reported the same impact of the increasing severity factor on holocellulose, lignin, and extractive fractions in OP hydrochars [41].

The FTIR and solid state C-13 NMR spectra were used to determine the effect of MHTC on the surface functional groups of dry OP. In Fig. S1, the FTIR spectra of OP biomass and hydrochars are shown in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} . Whereas in Fig. 1, the same spectra were presented in

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of raw material and hydrochars.

the range of 900–1800 cm^{-1} for a better interpretation of the spectral signals. In this specific region, the most significant changes in intensities and positions of the spectral signals were observed, which are characteristic for the structural components of biomass (hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin). In the case of hemicellulose, the peak at 1236 cm^{-1} has been associated with C–O–C bonds of acetyl groups [42], while the peak at 1740 cm^{-1} could be attributed to the vibrational stretching of the C=O present in acetoxy groups of xylans [43]. The increase in temperature and holding time resulted in a decrease in the intensity of the peak at 1236 cm^{-1} , especially in the hydrochars produced at 215 °C and 250 °C. On the other hand, the peak intensity at 1742 cm^{-1} reduced significantly in hydrochars 250–16 and 250–30. This indicated a substantial loss of hemicellulose in the hydrochars. With respect to cellulose, the intense peak centered at 1030 cm^{-1} has been associated with its C–O bonds [43]. The increase in MHTC severity generally resulted in the attenuation of this peak signal, and the appearance of a new peak (1056 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of hydrochars. This new peak corresponds to C–H bonds and could be formed due to hydrothermal treatment of cellulose fractions [37]. On the other hand, FTIR spectra in the lignin fingerprint region (1000–1800 cm^{-1}) revealed that the increase in MHTC severity led to the production of hydrochars enriched in lignin. The peak at 1708 cm^{-1} could be attributed to stretching vibrations in unconjugated carbonyl bonds of aldehydes or ketones, while the peaks at 1605 cm^{-1} and 1514 cm^{-1} are usually assigned to C=C bonds in aromatic rings [44]. Peaks at 1455 cm^{-1} and 1110 cm^{-1} are of C–H bonds in methyl groups of lignin [44]. All these peak signals were enhanced with the increase of MHTC severity, indicating a progressive enrichment of lignin in hydrochars. Furthermore, a decrease in peak intensity at 1645 cm^{-1} , characteristic of H–O–H bonds in adsorbed water [45] was observed. This suggested that the EMC in the hydrochars decreased with the increasing severity of MHTC and supported the findings on EMC (discussed in Section 3.3).

Solid state ^{13}C NMR spectra (Fig. 2) of OP and hydrochars showed the presence of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The peaks at 57–67 ppm (corresponding to O-alkyl carbons, C6), 70 ppm (C2,3,5), 80–92 ppm (OCH groups, C4), 102–108 ppm (C1), and 170 ppm (C=O groups) were signals of cellulose and hemicellulose. The C4 signal at 80–85 and 85–92 ppm was indicative of amorphous and crystalline cellulose, respectively [46]. Characteristic signals at 20 ppm (methyl) and 30 ppm (aliphatic methylene carbons) were indicative of hemicellulose [47,48]. Signals at 52–56 ppm (OCH₃), 100–112 ppm (acetal, C1), 135 ppm (aromatic C), and 142–160 ppm (aromatic C) were attributed to lignin [46,49]. The MHTC of OP resulted in changes in the hydrochars spectra. Compared to the OP spectra, the peak intensities at 20 ppm and 173 ppm decreased, and the peak intensity at 30 ppm increased and sharpened in the hydrochars produced at 180 °C-30 min onwards. This may indicate that the depolymerisation of hemicellulose intensified at 180 °C-30 min. Furthermore, an increase in MHTC severity resulted in a decrease in the peak intensity of amorphous cellulose (80–85 ppm), while the peak intensity of crystalline cellulose (85–92 ppm) became relatively sharper and increased. In addition, an increase in peak intensity at 55 ppm (especially from 215 °C-30 min),

Fig. 2. NMR spectra of raw material and hydrochars. The C, H, and L represents cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, respectively.

135 ppm, and 152 ppm indicated the gradual enrichment of lignin fractions with rising MHTC severity. The lignin enrichment was more pronounced in hydrochars produced at 250 °C. The reduction of the hemicellulose fraction could be due to its conversion into degradation products such as monosaccharides, oligosaccharides, and furfural [50]. In the literature, authors have also previously reported a decrease in hemicellulose and amorphous cellulose signals, and an enrichment of lignin in the solid state ^{13}C NMR analysis of hydrochars produced from olive tree trimmings [51] and textile wastes [52], or maple wood chars [53].

3.2. Physical, proximate, and ultimate characteristics of raw material and hydrochars

Table 2 presents the variations in the physical and proximate characteristics of the raw material and hydrochars. The MHTC of wet OP produced hydrochars with 51.98–91.24 % yield, 0.25–0.40 g cm $^{-3}$ BD, 68.17–79.06 % VM, 1.72–2.42 % ash, and 19.18–30.11 % FC contents. Increasing the MHTC severity factor from 3.050 to 5.929 decreased the hydrochar yield by 0.24–42.89 %. Likewise, compared to dry OP, the BD, VM, and ash contents in hydrochars fall by 23.65–52.9 %, 1.57–15.13 %, and 42.97–59.51 %, respectively. On the contrary, the amount of FC in the hydrochars increased by 24.26–95.07 %. These trends are due to the various reactions that occurred during the MHTC of OP. Intensification of hydrolysis, depolymerisation, dehydration, decarboxylation, and deoxygenation reactions could be responsible for the decrease in yield and VM. Whereas, escalation of polymerisation and aromatisation reactions could be reasons for the increase in FC [52,55, 56].

The fuel ratio (FC/VM) is a commonly used indicator that predicts the combustibility potential of hydrochars [18]. The hydrochars showed a fuel ratio range of 0.24–0.44, which was 26.24–129.84 % higher than OP with a 0.19 fuel ratio. High severity factor of MHTC led to the production of hydrochar with a lower VM and a higher FC. Consequently,

this hydrochar type showed a higher fuel ratio of 0.44 and better combustibility potential. The present findings are in confirmation of earlier studies on hydrochars produced from OP and other residual biomasses [18,57]. Lower ash content in hydrochars could be due to thermal degradation, increased solubility, and the transfer of inorganic minerals from OP to the liquid fraction, with increased MHTC severity [58,59]. This is an important advantage of hydrochar over lignite, which has a high ash content of up to 14.10 % [60]. Apart from the aforesaid positive characteristics of hydrochar, a non-favorable characteristic of lower BD was observed. A reduction in BD could be due to a decrease in VM and inorganic components [57]. This makes the hydrochar more voluminous and bulkier. Therefore, pelletisation of hydrochars is highly recommended to reduce transportation and storage costs.

Table 3 exhibits the ultimate characteristics of the raw material and hydrochars. Dry OP contained 57.44 % C, 7.39 % H, 1.48 % N, and 29.31 % O contents. Hydrochars produced under different severity conditions showed significant variations in the C (58.03–67.73 %), H (7.00–8.28 %), N (1.57–1.89 %), and O (20.86–30.63 %) contents. The S content was found to be less than 0.02 % in both OP and hydrochar and is therefore not reported in Table 3. The C content incremented by 2.25–17.85 %, while the O content reduced by 4.87–28.85 % in the hydrochars with the increase in process severity. In comparison to the present results, earlier studies reported the same trend with slightly higher C (61.1–70.97 %) but similar H (6.40–7.64 %), N (0.83–1.86 %) and O contents (20.24–24.3 %) in OP hydrochars [13,15,17,54]. These differences are due to the use of varied HTC conditions (220–260 °C, 30 min–24 h) and OP with different compositions in the literature and in the present study. More severe process conditions enhanced the C content of hydrochars because of intensified polymerisation and aromatisation reactions during HTC. Whereas, the decline in O content was due to the dominance of dehydration, decarboxylation, and deoxygenation reactions [52,61]. These reasons were also evident from the van Krevelen diagram of biomass and hydrochars (Fig. 3). An increase in severity factors from 4.015 to 5.929 of the MHTC process produced

Table 2
Physical and proximate characteristics of raw material and hydrochars on a dry basis.

Samples	HY (%)	BD (g cm ⁻³)	Ash (%)	VM (%)	FC (%)	FC/VM	References
OP	NA	0.52 ± 0.02	4.25 ± 0.14	80.31 ± 1.41	15.44 ± 1.54	0.19	Present work
OP	NA	NA	2.3	74.2	16.1	0.21	[13]
OP	NA	NA	9.0	66.7	16.6	0.24	[18]
OP	NA	NA	0.1	73.1	24.7	0.33	[54]
180-2	91.02 ± 1.77	0.37 ± 0.00	1.76 ± 0.37	79.06 ± 0.80	19.18 ± 1.11	0.24	Present work
180-16	91.24 ± 2.23	0.40 ± 0.01	1.99 ± 0.31	78.71 ± 0.47	19.30 ± 0.74	0.25	Present work
180-30	86.74 ± 0.79	0.38 ± 0.02	2.18 ± 0.22	77.94 ± 0.36	19.88 ± 0.30	0.26	Present work
215-2	71.06 ± 1.19	0.38 ± 0.04	2.28 ± 0.05	75.35 ± 0.68	22.37 ± 0.63	0.30	Present work
215-16	68.40 ± 1.98	0.30 ± 0.03	2.01 ± 0.28	75.09 ± 0.68	22.90 ± 0.68	0.30	Present work
215-16	67.57 ± 2.07	0.33 ± 0.04	2.42 ± 0.43	74.71 ± 0.47	22.87 ± 0.72	0.31	Present work
215-16	67.42 ± 2.97	0.32 ± 0.02	2.04 ± 0.05	74.93 ± 0.80	23.03 ± 0.82	0.31	Present work
215-30	54.71 ± 0.90	0.25 ± 0.00	1.93 ± 0.14	74.10 ± 1.30	23.98 ± 1.89	0.32	Present work
250-2	68.52 ± 1.59	0.25 ± 0.00	2.00 ± 0.09	71.05 ± 0.60	26.95 ± 0.56	0.38	Present work
250-16	63.32 ± 1.22	0.29 ± 0.03	2.03 ± 0.22	68.39 ± 0.65	29.58 ± 0.43	0.43	Present work
250-30	51.98 ± 1.11	0.28 ± 0.00	1.72 ± 0.17	68.17 ± 0.81	30.11 ± 0.67	0.44	Present work
250-30	56.0	NA	0.8	61.0	36.2	0.59	[13]
250-30	65.0	NA	5.4	56.9	36.1	0.63	[18]
220-90	65.8	NA	27.7	65.3	5.5	0.08	[54]
260-60	40.63 ± 2.02	NA	NA	66.77 ± 0.42	NA	NA	[17]

Note: NA means Not Available

hydrochars with relatively lower H/C (1.25–1.51) and O/C (0.24–0.32) atomic ratios than dry OP (H/C-1.53, O/C-0.40). This indicates an increased degree of carbonisation in these hydrochars due to elevated dehydration and decarbonylation-decarboxylation reactions, respectively [62]. Hydrochars produced at higher severity factors (5.071–5.929) exhibited resemblance to lignite coal. Volpe and Fiori (2017) and Gultekin et al. also reported similar findings for hydrochars derived from OP [58,59].

3.3. Energy and moisture sorption characteristics of raw material and hydrochars

Table 4 presents the HHV, LHV, EDR, EY, and EMC of dry OP and hydrochars. The LHV represents the more exact heating value of hydrochars after deducting the latent heat of vaporization of water (calculated based on H content). EDR is indicative of energy stored in a unit mass. The EMC is a crucial parameter in assessing the suitability of hydrochar for fuel applications and plays a significant role in determining its long-term storage stability and combustibility characteristics. It is derived from the moisture sorption curve of biomass and hydrochars (Fig. S2). The rise in severity of MHTC led to the production of hydrochars with beneficial fuel characteristics, i.e., higher HHV (24.46–28.45

Table 3
Ultimate characteristics of raw material and hydrochars on a dry basis.

Samples	C (%)	H (%)	N (%)	O (%)	References
OP	57.44 ± 0.98	7.39 ± 0.14	1.48 ± 0.35	29.31 ± 1.29	Present work
OP	48.30	6.73	1.26	43.71	[16]
OP	46.6	5.9	1.4	NA	[54]
OP	53.86±0.12	7.28 ± 0.02	1.13±0.03	37.53±0.11	[17]
OP	42.80	5.65	2.01	46.51	[15]
180-2	58.03 ± 0.55	7.53 ± 0.01	1.84 ± 0.13	30.63 ± 0.52	Present work
180-16	59.87 ± 1.23	7.78 ± 0.22	1.73 ± 0.17	28.75 ± 1.93	Present work
180-30	61.60 ± 0.01	7.92 ± 0.10	1.89 ± 0.03	26.42 ± 0.24	Present work
215-2	62.42 ± 2.75	7.90 ± 0.49	1.62 ± 0.03	25.77 ± 3.13	Present work
215-16	61.94 ± 1.25	7.57 ± 0.28	1.60 ± 0.12	27.02 ± 1.45	Present work
215-16	63.66 ± 1.25	7.73 ± 0.22	1.63 ± 0.09	24.30 ± 1.52	Present work
215-16	63.30 ± 1.08	7.85 ± 0.20	1.65 ± 0.09	25.14 ± 1.42	Present work
215-30	66.64 ± 1.07	8.28 ± 0.20	1.60 ± 0.01	21.50 ± 1.44	Present work
250-2	64.77 ± 1.59	7.88 ± 0.09	1.59 ± 0.10	23.64 ± 1.64	Present work
250-16	67.73 ± 0.31	7.00 ± 0.07	1.57 ± 0.00	20.86 ± 0.66	Present work
250-30	66.31 ± 0.69	7.73 ± 0.15	1.68 ± 0.06	22.50 ± 0.57	Present work
250-30	67.8 ± 0.4	6.5 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.1	24.3 ± 0.4	[13]
220-90	61.1	6.4	0.9	NA	[54]
260-60	70.97±0.18	6.80 ± 0.00	0.83±0.06	21.41±0.25	[17]
220-24	67.90	7.64	1.86	20.24	[15]
Lignite	49.70–73.91	4.25–6.23	0.80–2.82	12.97–24.40	[60]

Note: NA means Not Available

Fig. 3. van Krevelen diagram for raw material and hydrochars.

MJ/kg), LHV (22.92–27.12 MJ/kg), and EDR (1.07–1.25), along with reduced EMC (31.1–84.7 mg/g). These properties were improved by 6.72–25.43 %, 6.90–26.49 %, 6.72–25.43 %, and 31.31–74.78 %, respectively, compared to OP. In accordance with the present findings, previous studies also reported the same impact of process severity on the characteristics of OP hydrochars. The OP hydrochar produced at the elevated MHTC severity (5.929) showed a higher HHV (28.45 MJ/kg) than previously reported data. Missaoui et al. reported that OP

Table 4

Energy and moisture sorption characteristics of raw material and hydrochars on a dry basis.

Samples	HHV (MJ/kg)	LHV (MJ/kg)	EDR	EY	EMC (mg/g)
OP	22.92 ± 0.24	21.44	1.00	100	123.3
180-2	24.46 ± 0.24	22.92	1.07	97.13	84.1
180-16	24.68 ± 0.22	23.10	1.08	98.25	84.7
180-30	24.67 ± 0.37	23.06	1.08	93.36	81.9
215-2	25.50 ± 1.09	23.88	1.11	79.06	70.4
215-16	26.09 ± 0.71	24.50	1.14	77.86	60.3
215-16	25.99 ± 0.38	24.40	1.13	76.64	61.5
215-16	26.07 ± 0.64	24.46	1.14	76.69	64.3
215-30	26.85 ± 0.39	25.13	1.17	64.10	61.6
250-2	27.24 ± 1.01	25.57	1.19	81.43	39.1
250-16	28.08 ± 0.54	26.44	1.22	77.58	36.4
250-30	28.75 ± 0.53	27.12	1.25	65.20	31.1

hydrochar, produced at 250 °C with a holding time of 30 min showed an HHV of 27.6 MJ/kg and an EDR of 1.2 [13]. Similarly, Semaan et al. observed an HHV of 25.6 MJ/kg and an EDR of 1.26 for OP hydrochar produced at 280 °C with a 30-minute holding time [18].

The increase in heating value could be due to lignin enrichment in hydrochars with increasing process severity. This is because lignin has a higher heating value than the cellulose and hemicellulose fractions [39, 63]. As the severity of the MHTC raised, the cellulose and hemicellulose fractions decreased due to their hydrolysis, but the lignin resisted hydrolysis and was enriched due to its recalcitrant aromatic chemical structure. For this is reason, the hydrochar produced at high severity contained relatively higher levels of lignin and HHV. This hydrochar also showed the relatively lowest EMC (31.1 mg/g), which was reduced by 74.78 % with respect to raw dry OP (123.3 mg/g). Data on the EMC of OP hydrochars are not available in the literature for comparison. However, in agreement with the present findings, Aguado et al. also reported that the most severe conditions ($\log R_0 = 7.68$) reduced the EMC of hydrochars derived from almond tree pruning by 80 % compared to raw almond tree pruning [37]. The decrease in EMC of hydrochars with increasing process severity could be due to the loss of hygroscopic hydroxyl groups (characteristic of polysaccharides) and the enrichment of hydrophobic lignin fractions. This increases the

hydrophobic character of the material [64]. Lower EMC in hydrochars is an indicator of their potential for improved combustion performance [28,65].

3.4. Slagging and fouling indices for raw material and hydrochars

The mineral composition (Na_2O , K_2O , MgO , CaO , P_2O_5 , Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , and TiO_2) of dry OP and hydrochars is presented in Table S3 (Supplementary Information). On basis of these data, different slagging and fouling indices (AI, B/A ratio, SI, FI, SVI, and BAI) of dry OP and hydrochars were determined (Fig. 4). The dry OP biomass showed 1.17 kg/GJ AI, 20.59 B/A, 0.21 SI, 55.43 FI, 12.07 SVI, and 0.04 BAI. Comparatively, hydrochars showed 0.16–0.92 kg/GJ AI, 4.76–11.12 B/A, 0.05–0.11 SI, 2.18–18.54 FI, 13.25–21.36 SVI, and 0.01–0.11 BAI. Hydrochar produced at the highest severity had relatively lower AI (0.16 kg/GJ), SI (0.05), and FI (2.18), which were reductions of 86.53 %, 76.89 %, and 96.07 %, respectively, compared to OP. The decrease in AI was due to an increase in HHV and a decrease in K and Na content in high-severity hydrochar. Lower SI was due to a decrease in basic oxides, retention of acidic oxides, and very low S content in hydrochar. The decrease in FI of hydrochars was due to the reduced concentrations of alkali and alkaline earth metals. The SVI (21.03) and BAI (0.11) increased by 75.11 % and 165.22 %, respectively, in the highest severity hydrochar, compared to OP. The SVI was elevated because of the accumulation of SiO_2 and the deduction in the Ca, Mg, and Fe concentrations in the hydrochar. An increase in BAI may be due to lower Fe concentrations in the hydrochar. Similar results have been reported in the literature for hydrochar produced from agricultural waste [66] and sewage sludge [67].

A ternary plot (Fig. 4) was also used to estimate the slagging-fouling risk based on the initial deformation temperature (IDT) of minerals present in OP and hydrochars. Despite the above-mentioned positive results for hydrochar in terms of slagging and fouling indices, the ternary plot showed that the OP and its hydrochars have a high slagging and fouling risk. The reason is that they contain a relatively higher amount of minerals with low initial deformation (melting) temperatures, i.e., Na_2O , K_2O , and P_2O_5 , than minerals with higher initial deformation melting temperatures, i.e., CaO , MgO , Fe_2O_3 , and Al_2O_3 .

Fig. 4. Ternary plot with slagging and fouling indices for raw material and hydrochars.

[33]. This is problematic because silica can react with alkali minerals with low melting temperatures and make eutectics that can cause slagging [34]. Nevertheless, a progression of high severity hydrochars from the high slagging-fouling risk region to the nearby moderate region was observed.

3.5. Response surface optimisation for hydrochar production with best fuel characteristics

The experimental data on HY, EMC, HHV, and LHV were mathematically modeled by applying ANOVA analysis with a 95 % confidence level. Table 5 shows the parameter values of the four mathematical models (Eq. 1), as well as the regression coefficients R^2 and R^2 adjust. In all cases, the models were statistically significant (p -values < 0.0001), while the regression coefficient (R^2), which represents the goodness of fit between experimental and predicted data, was higher than 0.991. This can also be seen in Fig. S3 for the four responses studied.

Fig. 5 shows the 3D response surfaces and 2D contour plots generated by applying Eq. (1) with the parameters given in Table 5 and for temperatures and reaction times in the ranges 180–250 °C and 2–30 min, respectively. In the case of hydrochar yield (Fig. 5a), the highest values were obtained for the lowest reaction temperature (180 °C) combined with low reaction times. Thus, the model predicted a maximum HY value of 92.8 % under the conditions of 180 °C-10.6 min, where mainly a loss of aqueous extractives would occur. As can be seen in the coefficient plot, expressed in coded form in Fig. S4-a, the value of HY is negatively influenced by two linear terms (T_R and t_R), a quadratic term ($T_R \times t_R$) and an interaction term ($T_R \times t_R$), while the quadratic term ($T_R \times T_R$) has a positive effect on HY. This leads to a reduction in HY with increasing temperature and time during the MHTC, although the hydrolytic effect is less pronounced at higher temperatures, particularly at shorter reaction times. The mathematical model also revealed that the hydrochar recovery is strongly reduced above 220 °C for reaction times longer than 15 min, which could be explained by the fact that at this temperature cellulose starts to undergo significant hydrolysis during hydrothermal treatments [63]. The minimum value of HY (50.4 %) was obtained for the conditions of 243 °C-30 min. In comparison, Eres Yay et al. reported a slightly higher HY of 53 % at a higher temperature (260 °C) and longer holding time (60 min) than the present study [16]. This suggests that MHTC could be used to achieve similar HY at a lower temperature and shorter holding time, compared to HTC.

For the EMC of the hydrochars, the mathematical model showed that this parameter is strongly influenced by the reaction temperature and, to a much lesser extent, by the treatment time (Fig. S4-b). The mathematical model predicted a maximum EMC value of 86.5 mg/g for the hydrochar obtained at 180 °C-2 min and a minimum value of 31.9 mg/g under the conditions of 250 °C-23.3 min (Fig. 5b). Considering that the EMC value for the dry raw OP is 123.3 mg/g, the application of MHTC caused a significant reduction of more than 74.0 % in the EMC content of the hydrochars. The experimental values of HHV and LHV showed excellent fits to the model (Eq. 1), as indicated by the R^2 data in Table 5. According to Figs. S4-c and S4-d, temperature and reaction time exert a positive effect on HHV and LHV, with the two linear terms of the models (T_R and t_R) being much more significant than the quadratic term ($T_R \times T_R$) and the interaction term ($T_R \times t_R$). This implies that the maximum values of HHV and LHV (28.9 MJ/kg and 27.2 MJ/kg, respectively) are

achieved by MHTC of OP at 250 °C for 30 min, as shown in Figs. 5c and 5d. The HHV value for this hydrochar is similar to that reported by other authors (29 MJ/kg) when OP was hydrothermally treated at 240 °C for 60 min [16]. In this study, the HHV was increased by 26.1 % compared to the original feedstock. In another study, Cheng et al. reported an optimised condition of 220 °C-60 min for the production of coconut shell hydrochar with a maximum HHV value of 29.39 MJ/kg [68].

3.6. Combustion performance of biomass and hydrochars

The thermogravimetric (TG) curves (Figs. 6a and 6b) illustrate that heating both OP and hydrochar (250–30) resulted in a continuous loss of weight until temperatures above 600 °C were reached, where the values stabilised and indicated the weight of the ash in the samples. Furthermore, the TG (Fig. 6b) and DSC (Fig. 6d) curves were divided into three zones (Zone 1, Zone 2, and Zone 3) to facilitate their interpretation. In zone 1, from room temperature to slightly above 100 °C, the materials dry. Within this region, the DTG analysis of the raw OP showed a more pronounced signal of moisture, reinforcing the notion that the hydrochar has a more hydrophobic character than the original biomass. Zone 2 extends in the range of 141–375 °C for the raw OP and 120.8–403 °C for the hydrochar. Here, thermal decomposition of certain biomass components (mainly hemicellulose, cellulose, and, to a lesser extent, lignin) and release of VM occur. The VM undergoes gas phase combustion at temperatures above the ignition temperature (T_i), causing the DSC curves to shift from negative values (due to the endothermic nature of the pyrolysis reactions) to positive values (attributable to the exothermic nature of the combustion reactions). For the raw OP, the DTG curve in zone 2 displays a shoulder at 270 °C and a peak at 320.0 °C, which could be associated with the removal of VM derived from hemicellulose and cellulose, respectively. Numerous studies have reported that hemicellulose produces volatiles at relatively lower temperatures than cellulose [69,70]. The DTG signal at 270 °C for the hydrochar 250–30 exhibited a significant reduction in the VM signal compared to the raw OP. This could be due to a loss of hemicellulose content in the hydrochar. On the other hand, the DTG peak that appeared at 320.0 °C for the raw OP was replaced by a new signal of higher intensity at 312.5 °C, in the hydrochar. This increase in signal intensity could be attributed to the higher susceptibility of the treated cellulose to generate VM than the original cellulose, considering the lower cellulose content of the hydrochar (3.0 %) as opposed to the raw OP (12.15 %). The heterogeneous combustion of the solids generated in zone 2 takes place in zone 3. For the OP, a prominent peak at 420 °C and a shoulder centered around 460 °C were observed (Fig. 6b). The first signal could be attributed to the combustion of holocellulose fractions of the hydrochar, while the second signal could be from the combustion of solids derived from lignin. The intense signal at 420 °C in the DTG analysis of the raw OP was transformed into two small peaks at 419 °C and 428 °C in the hydrochar 250–30, which could be due to the combustion of its cellulose and hemicellulose fractions.

Regarding the exothermic energy flows obtained from the DSC analyses (Figs. 6b and 6d), it was evident that MHTC caused a significant shift of the signals from zone 3 to zone 2. Thus, for the dry raw OP, the energy emissions from combustion in zones 1 and 2 accounted for 31.3 % and 68.7 % of the total, respectively, with maximum heat flux values of 106.3 kW/kg (zone 2) and 224.4 kW/kg (zone 3). In contrast,

Table 5
Model parameters (β_i) and regression coefficients (R^2 and R^2 adjust) for the models representing HY, EMC, HHV, and LHV of the hydrochars.

Response	β_0	β_1	β_2	β_3	β_4	β_5	R^2	R^2 adjust
HY, %	537	- 4.04	1.52	0.00869	0.0192	0.00626	0.991	0.983
EMC, mg/g	15.5	1.18	- 0.732	- 0.00433	0.0158	NS	0.994	0.990
HHV, MJ/kg	25.3	- 0.0361	- 0.106	0.000173	NS	0.000664	0.994	0.990
LHV, MJ/kg	24.7	- 0.0436	- 0.120	0.000186	NS	0.000719	0.996	0.993

Note: Models obtained from Eq. (1); Data are shown with three significant figures.; NS: not statistical significance.

Fig. 5. Response surface plots corresponding to: (a) HY; (b) EMC; (c) HHV; and (d) LHV.

for hydrochar 250–30, the emissions were 56.8 % in zone 2 and 43.2 % in zone 3, with maximum energy fluxes of 140.2 kW/kg and 104.1 kW/kg, respectively. Therefore, MHTC resulted in a more energetically homogeneous biofuel, allowing for the generation of similar amounts of thermal energy in both combustion zones. This could indicate that the combustion of hydrochar is less intense and produces more stable flames compared to the raw OP.

From the thermogravimetric analyses, the values of $(dw/dt)_{\max}$, $(dw/dt)_{\text{mean}}$, T_i and T_f were calculated both for the raw OP (9.12 %/min, 1.04 %/min, 197.3 °C, and 498.4 °C, respectively) and for the hydrochar 250–30 (7.44 %/min, 1.06 %/min, 224.3 °C, and 533.4 °C, respectively). The higher T_i value for the hydrochar, compared to the raw material, could be explained by its lower VM content and would imply a lower risk of spontaneous combustion of the hydrochar. Cuevas et al. also obtained significant increases in T_i when olive fruit endocarps ($T_i = 251.4$ °C) were subjected to hydrothermal treatment at 250 °C ($T_i = 294.5$ °C) [36]. The comprehensive combustibility index (S) was $4.90 \times 10^{-7} \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ °C}^{-3}$ (raw OP) and $2.94 \times 10^{-7} \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ °C}^{-3}$ (hydrochar 250–30). The literature suggests that values of $S > 2.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ min}^{-2} \text{ °C}^{-3}$ could be suitable for use as a biofuel [71]. Therefore, hydrochar 250–30 would have good reactivity for use as a fuel, although it would be lower than that of the raw OP.

4. Conclusions

The present study demonstrated that microwave-assisted hydrothermal carbonisation of olive pomace slurry from the olive oil industry could be used to produce hydrochar fuel for potential combustion

application. Temperature was found to be a major factor that directly controlled the process severity, the thermo-chemical reactions, and the characteristics of the hydrochars. Microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation at 180 °C for 30 min onwards resulted in more pronounced depolymerisation of hemicellulose in the olive pomace. Whereas, the treatment at 250 °C (high severity) caused more aromatization and lignin enrichment in the hydrochars. Consequently, high severity hydrochars exhibited better fuel characteristics (comparable to lignite), specifically in terms of lower ash content, equilibrium moisture content, slagging-fouling indices, and higher fuel ratio, energy densification, HHV, LHV, and combustion performance. The optimum microwave-hydrothermal carbonisation process conditions were 250 °C and 30 min for the production of olive pomace hydrochar, which is comparatively faster than an earlier reported conventional hydrothermal carbonisation process (60 min and more). Moreover, the microwave reactors used for hydrochar production could also be more sustainable because they don't pose the risk of reactor material corrosion and metal contamination that commonly occur in conventional steel reactors.

Major challenges to the practical application of high severity hydrochars for fuel applications were identified to be their lower yield and bulk density, along with the presence of minerals (containing potassium and sodium) with low melting temperatures. Therefore, to overcome these challenges, future research studies on pelletisation of these hydrochars using clay minerals (e.g., bentonite) are necessary. This will facilitate the practical application of hydrochar as a substitute fuel for coal by making its transportation and feeding easier and safer (less deteriorating) for cooking stoves, industrial boilers and power plants.

Fig. 6. TG curves (a, c) and DTG curves and exothermic heat flow curves from DSC analyses (b, d) under an oxidative atmosphere at 10 °C min^{-1} for the raw material and the hydrochar obtained at 250 °C for 30 min (250–30).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jaap.2024.106801](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2024.106801).

Data Availability

Extended dataset with the title “Production of hydrochar fuel by microwave hydrothermal carbonisation of olive pomace slurry from olive oil industry for combustion application” for the present publication is available on the Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13695542>). This dataset is openly accessible under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license and includes the following data files: (1) Dataset description.txt (provides abbreviations or codes of samples and their properties). (2) Extended dataset V1.0.xlsx (data files for the biochemical, proximate, ultimate, HHV, and mineral characteristics of the raw material (two-phase olive pomace slurry) and hydrochars) (3) ^{13}C NMR data.zip (raw data files for ^{13}C -solid nuclear magnetic resonance analysis of raw material and hydrochars). (4) TGA-DTA data.zip (raw data for thermal gravimetric analysis of raw material and hydrochars) (5) FTIR data.zip (raw data for fourier transform infrared analysis of raw material and hydrochars).

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